

Heart Disease Prediction using Machine Learning Models

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Abstract:

Machine learning and artificial intelligence have played an important role in the development of many disciplines, especially with the growth of knowledge in recent years. It can be more reliable and diagnose diseases faster. Therefore, machine learning algorithms are increasingly used to predict many diseases. Designs can also help us detect and identify errors to improve ad consistency and accuracy. We looked at how to diagnose heart disease using several machine learning algorithms. Heart disease is a serious disease that affects the heart. Because heart disease can be life-threatening, researchers are focusing on developing smart systems to accurately diagnose heart disease based on electronic medical records with the help of machine learning algorithms. If this information is anticipated well in advance, it can provide important insights to physicians who can tailor diagnosis and treatment to the patient's condition. The research in this report shows that it's a two-step process. The heart dataset is first prepared in the required format to run the machine learning algorithm. Medical records and other information about patients are collected through the Kaggle platform. Then use the heart disease information to determine if the patient has heart disease. Second, this article offers several useful results. Check the accuracy of machine learning algorithms such as Logistic regression, K-nearest neighbour and random forest from the confusion matrix. Current research results show that the Logistic Regression algorithm has an accuracy of up to 95% compared to other algorithms.

Keywords: Heart disease prediction, machine learning, random forest, K-Nearest Neighbour, Logistic regression.

I.Introduction

The term "heart disease" refers to a group of diseases that affect the heart. According to the World Health Organization, cardiovascular disease is currently the leading cause of death worldwide and is responsible for approximately 17.9 million deaths. Cardiovascular disease (CVD), commonly referred to as heart disease, includes many conditions that affect the heart, and the two most common are ischemic heart disease and stroke. The World Health Organization has listed the most important behavioural risk factors for CVD, including poor diet, sedentary lifestyle, smoking and drinking too much alcohol. Long-term exposure to these risk factors can be the first sign of cardiovascular disease, including high blood pressure, high blood sugar, high blood lipids and

obesity. Warning signs defined by the American Heart Association include the development of one or more of the following symptoms: shortness of breath, persistent cough or wheezing, swelling of the ankles and feet, fatigue, loss of appetite, and thinking problems. Additionally, coronaviruses can cause heart disease. Effective early detection can reduce the risk and global burden of heart disease with prompt initiation of treatment to prevent further health problems. Therefore, it is necessary to develop machine learning models that can predict the probability of developing CVD based on risk factors.

Recently, machine learning models have been used successfully in many medical fields. They help in a good analysis, evaluation and prediction of different treatments. In this report, we present a machine learning method that can predict whether a patient has heart disease based on basic health information.

Machine learning (ML) is part of artificial intelligence (AI) and allows software to improve prediction accuracy without formal work. To predict the new output, machine learning algorithms use historical data as input. Machine learning is important and changes with progress and practice. Therefore, machine learning has become a major challenge for many organizations. Machine learning includes supervised, unsupervised, semi-supervised and discrete reinforcement learning to find truth from predictions and data.

Machine learning algorithms can create models based on data models called decision making or predictive data. The use of machine learning in the medical industry is current research that mainly aims to mimic certain human activities or mental processes and to identify diseases from various materials. Even though heart disease can occur in various forms, there is a common set of core risk factors that influence whether someone will ultimately be at a risk for heart disease or not.

Fig. (1.a) – Human Heart

Fig (1.b) - Outline of Heart disease prediction

Prediction of cardiovascular disease using machine learning techniques using training and test data neural network algorithms [6]. The K-nearest neighbour algorithm has been used to diagnose heart disease [7]. Several effective algorithms have been used to detect HD and the results show that each algorithm has its own power to register targets [8]. Monitoring networks have been used to diagnose HD [9]. The report will develop a machine learning prediction model to help determine heart disease history. Data is collected from Kaggle dataset, which

includes clinical information and patient characteristics. This information will be used to predict whether the patient has had a heart attack. For the diagnosis of the HD dataset, we consider 14 characteristics of the patients. It identifies the presence or absence of the disease and can help us diagnose the disease with less medication. In this study, patients' age, gender, cholesterol, blood pressure, blood pressure, etc. Three different machine learning algorithms are used for the classification and prediction of heart disease: Logistic Regression (LR), K Nearest Neighbour(KNN), and Random Forest (RF). This report offers many interesting results. The objects of the given data are trained under the following algorithms. The accuracy of the algorithm is compared and evaluated according to the characteristics of high-definition data sets. All selected machine learning algorithms were found to be effective with an accuracy rate of over 80%. The best algorithm is Logistic Regression (LR), which gives us about 95% accuracy. Finally, logistic regression (LR) algorithms will be considered to predict and diagnose heart disease in patients. This report is rotated periodically. Section 2 discusses the method. Section 3 briefly reviews various machine learning algorithms. Results and analyses are shown in section 4. In the results section, the algorithms for the confusion matrix are compared. Finally, Section 5 draws conclusions and future opportunities.

II. Literature Survey

With the continuous development of machine learning therapy, in recent years has conducted many experiments and researches and published important documents.

[1] Purushottam et al presented a paper entitled "Effective Cardiac Prediction System" using hill climbing and decision tree algorithms. They used the Cleveland dataset and preprocessed the data before using the classification algorithm. The Knowledge Extraction is done with Evolutionary Learning (KEEL), an open source data mining tool that collects missing values in data. The decision tree follows the order from top to bottom. For each correct point selected by the hill climb algorithm, nodes are selected from each test level. The parameters and their values are confidence levels. The minimum confidence level is 0.25. The actual system is about 86.7%.

[2] Santana Krishnan. J et al presented a paper titled "Drug Decision Using Machine Learning Algorithms," which uses decision trees and the unknown Bayesian algorithm to predict heart disease. In the decision tree algorithm, the tree is created using certain conditions that make a right or wrong decision. SVM, KNN, etc. algorithms like these are based on vertically or horizontally split events with possible outcomes depending on the variable. They also used the Cleveland dataset. The dataset is divided into 70% training and 30% testing using some methods. The accuracy of this algorithm is 91%. The second algorithm is the Naive Bayes algorithm used for classification. The accuracy of the algorithm reaches 87%.

[3] Article "Patience Using Machine Learning Algorithms" by Sonam Nikhar et al. Chapter Studies provides a description of the Naive Bayes and Decision Tree classifiers used specifically to predict heart disease.

[4] Aditi Gavhane et al presented a paper called "Decision Making using Machine Learning" in which the neural network algorithm Multilayer Perceptron is used to train and test knowledge. In this algorithm there will be an input layer and an output layer, and one or more layers are hidden between the two input and output layers. Through layers, each input and output are connected to layer. Serious weight is given to the connection. Another input is called Bias and gives weight as needed and the connection of nodes can be used for support or advice. Chapter

[5] Avinash Golande et al. presented the presentation "Using Advanced Learning Systems for Cardiovascular Diseases" Section uses a variety of data mining techniques to support doctors in distinguishing between heart disease. Commonly used methods are, nearest neighbors, decision trees and Naive Bayes.

[6] Lakshmana Rao et al proposed "Machine Learning Technology Prediction for Heart Disease" which has many factors related to heart disease. So, the difference between heart disease is difficult. Different neural networks and data mining were used to determine the severity of heart disease in people.

[7] Abhay Kishore et al. presented "Heart Attack Prediction Using Interactive Learning" in which heart attack prediction system by using Deep learning techniques and to predict the probable aspects of heart related infections of the patient Recurrent Neural System is used. This model uses deep learning and data mining to provide the most accurate model with the least possible errors. This paper acts as strong reference model for another type of heart attack prediction models.

[8] Senthil Kumar Mohan et al, proposed “Effective Heart Disease Prediction Using Hybrid Machine Learning Techniques” in which their main objective is to improve exactness in cardiovascular problems. The algorithms used are KNN, LR, SVM, NN to produce an improved exhibition level with a precision level of 88.7% through the prediction model for heart disease with hybrid random forest with linear model (HRFLM).

[9] Anjan N. Repaka et al. proposed a model demonstrating the performance of binary classification models was proposed, evaluated and compared with previous studies. Experimental

results show that our proposed method improves accuracy in finding the percentage of risk compared to other methods.

[10] Aakash Chauhan et al. Data were obtained directly from the electronic database and reduced to workbooks. Less help and more advice provide better prediction of heart disease. Patient data were extracted for active growth associations to establish strong associations.

III. Methodology

A. Data Collection: Data were collected from Kaggle [13]. The dataset contains a total of 303 cases with 13 features, as shown in Table 2. It is used to generate data, which makes previous data very important. In addition to manipulating data, resampling, and using custom options, data manipulation includes cleaning data by removing invalid or missing data items, messages, and letters.

B. Data Preprocessing: The effectiveness of machine learning models depends on the quality of the data used to build the models, which makes prior data very important. In addition to manipulating data, resampling, and using custom options, data manipulation includes cleaning data by removing invalid or missing data items, messages, and letters.

Table 1: List of Outliers

Attributes	Outlier Values
Age	None
Chol	417, 564, 394, 407, 409
Trestbps	172, 178, 180, 180, 200, 174, 192, 178, 180
Thalach	71
Oldpeak	4.2, 6.2, 5.6, 4.2, 4.4

i) Data Visualization and Cleaning: First we checked for missing values but found nothing. Second, we analysed the outliers as shown in Table 1 and found some outliers. Use (1) and (2) to analyse uncertainty; where IQR is the difference between the data distribution index and Q1, Q3 are the lower and upper quartiles, respectively. $(75\% \times Q3) + 3 \times IQR$ (1) $(25\% \times Q1) - 3 \times IQR$ (2) removes more points from the first expression. Similarly, data points smaller than the second indicator are lost. As a result, 2 out of 303 cases were removed. Then, a correlation coefficient matrix was obtained to evaluate the relationship between different attributes and output. Figure (2.a) explain the correlation matrix, in which the coefficients show the strength as well as the direction (positive or negative) of the relationship between the variables.

Fig (2.a) – Correlation Coefficient Matrix

Data Element	Description	Type	Range	Remarks
Age	-	Num ^a	29-77	Average is 54.37
Sex	-	Bi ^b	0: Female 1: Male	32% Female 68% Male
Cp	Chest pain level	Nom ^c	0/1/2/3 0: Asymptotic 2: non-anginal pain 3: Typical angina	Majority have 0 pain
Trestbps	Rest blood pressure	Num	94-200	Average is 131.6
Chol	Cholesterol level	Num	126-564	Average is 246.3
Fbs	Fasting blood sugar level	Bi	0: Level below 120 1: Level above 120	-
Restecg	Resting electrocardiographic results	Nom	0/1/2 0: Showing probable or definite left ventricular hypertrophy 2: Abnormal	-
Thalach	Maximum heart rate achieved	Num	71-202	-
Exang	Exercise induced angina	Bi	0: None 1: Produced	-
Oldpeak	ST depression induced by exercise relative to rest	Num	0-6.2	Right skewed data, majority of population is between 0 and 0.5
Slope	The slope of the peak exercise ST segment	Nom	0: Unsloping 1: Flat 2: Down-sloping	-
Ca	Number of major vessels	Nom	0/1/2/3/4	-
Thal	Defect type	Nom	1: Fixed defect 2: Normal 3: Reversible defect	There is one outlier of category 0
Target	Diagnosis of heart disease	Bi	0: No disease 1: Disease	-

Table 2: Heart disease dataset prediction

ii. Checking for Imbalances: The instability of the output will affect the accuracy of the estimation. Thus, the output "goal" balance is confirmed as shown in Figure 2b. When checked, the data is equal between the two classes at a ratio of 9:11. Therefore, there is no need to modify the data.

Fig (2.b) – Histogram and boxplot of the output Target

iii. Data Transformation: Use variables when files contain different files or when combining different files. In this case, nominal properties are converted to properties for use.

iv. Dimensionality Reduction: In machine learning, dimensionality reduction refers to the process of reducing the number of features through feature selection or extraction to reduce complexity and avoid overfitting. Specific selection is made by selecting a set of features from the original set, which can be done by methods such as CFS (correlation-based selection), chi-square test, and ridge regression. Slightly different from feature selection, feature extraction is the generation of new features from an original feature set. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is widely used. Calculates the projection of the original data onto a small area.

v. Data Splitting: In machine learning, data is usually divided into training set and test set; where the training set is used to train the model and the test set is used to evaluate the model and predict the output. This program uses Hold-out where 80% of the data is used for training and 20% for testing.

C. Machine Learning Algorithms: Data analysis techniques called machine learning automate the development of analytical models. In this study, three different algorithms are examined for the accuracy of finding the optimal solution.

3.1. Logistic Regression Model:

This type of machine learning is often used in classification and prediction, also known as Logistic regression. It is also used to predict random results in sets of independent variables, such as binary results. A binary value means that two possibilities will occur: the event will happen (i.e., 1) or it will not (i.e., 0). The following is the function of the logistic regression model.

Fig (3.a) – Logistic Regression Model

where z is a function of x_1, x_2, w_1, w_2 and b . So, z is a linear equation that provides a sigmoid function to estimate the output. We calculate the loss to evaluate the effectiveness of this model. In this case, we use the cross-entropy loss function.

3.2. K-Nearest Neighbours (K-NN):

K-NN is the simplest classification system based on supervised learning. However, the K-NN algorithm can also be used for regression, but mainly for classification [18]. Identify new data points using the K-NN algorithm as they are similar to existing stored data. This demonstrates that the K-NN algorithm can quickly classify new data when it appears in the appropriate category, see fig. Figure 3.b.

Fig (3.b) – K-Nearest Neighbor

Here, the horizontal x -axis and vertical y -axis are independent and dependent on the position change, respectively. Figure 3.b is a simple example of the K-NN classification algorithm. In this algorithm, the test pattern (yellow square with characters) should be classified as a green triangle or a red star. Considering $k = 3$ in the small circle, the yellow circle will be the green triangle because most of the numbers in this area are green triangles and is not a red star. Now if we take $k = 7$ in the big circle with points, then the yellow circle will be the red star because the red star is four and the green triangle is three. So, it can be concluded that most of the custom fields are important here.

3.3. Random Forest:

Random Forest (RF) is a popular supervised machine learning algorithm used for classification and retrieval. However, it is mainly used to classify problems. The RF algorithm is based on the idea of group study. Part Cooperative Learning is a general learning technique that can be used with various learning algorithms to find better performance [2, 19]. It is worth noting that a common method is better than a decision tree () because it reduces competition by averaging the results (). The large number of decision trees in RF helped us achieve accuracy and avoid the overfitting problem. The following procedure is performed by the RF algorithm, see Figure 3.c.

- Step 1: First, choose n random samples from the given data Section.
- Step 2: A decision tree is created for each people.
- Step 3: Each decision tree predicts the output.

Step 4: Final result is reached by majority vote or average.

Fig (3.c) - General Procedure of Random Forest

D. Evaluation metrics: Evaluation metrics are used to test quality and machine learning model performance. In this document, the best model was selected based on the following evaluation metrics (Fig a):

Predicted class

Actual class

True positive (TP)	False negative (FN)
False positive (FP)	True negative (TN)

Fig (a) - Evaluation Metrics

i. Confusion matrix: N*N matrix where N is number of predicted classes. For the prediction problem confusion of two possible outputs, as in this work the size of the matrix is 2*2. The elements of the matrix are the numbers of correct ones and incorrect predictions, separated by class. For example, a True Positive is the number of correctly classified Positive class (in this case, the number of correctly diagnosed heart disease). Similarly, True Negative is a count correctly classified Negative class (In this case count correctly predicted absence of heart disease).

ii. Accuracy: Percentage of the total predictions that were classified correctly and are retrieved from the confusion matrix according to the following equation:

$$A = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}$$

iii. Precision: The percentage of positive cases that were classified correctly and is recovered from confusion matrix according to the following equation:

$$PR = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

iv. Sensitivity or Recall: Percentage of true value positive cases that were classified correctly, and is obtained from the confusion matrix according to the following equation:

$$RE = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

v. F1 Score: If the goal is to achieve the best accuracy and Recall that measuring F would be the best choice because it provides a harmonic mean recall and precision values classification problem and is obtained from confusion matrix according to the following equation:

$$F1 = \frac{2TP}{2TP + FP + FN}$$

IV. Results and discussion

A. Analysis of heart disease dataset:

Earlier than going to have a look at the performance of thinking about device gaining knowledge of algorithms in this research, analysis of the capabilities of coronary heart disease dataset could be centered on here. The full range of observations within the target attributes is 1025, wherein not having coronary heart ailment 499 (denoted by way of 0) and having coronary heart sickness 526 (represented by way of 1). So, the percentage of now not having heart disorder is 45.7%, and the percentage of having coronary heart sickness is 54.3%, see figure 4.b. It is proven that the charge of coronary heart disorder is greater than the price of no heart disorder. In figure 4.c, the sex feature of the HD dataset is discovered through the goal feature.

Figure (4.a) shows the target class.

Fig (4.a) – Target Class

In sex attribute, the girl and male numbers are 312 and 713, respectively. So, the male number is extra than double of lady number. We will see in this diagram 8.c that the wide variety of heart diseases in adult males is better than in females. Further, no heart disease amongst males is higher than in females.

Diagram (4.c) concludes that male is victim than woman.

Fig (4.b) – Percentage of no heart disease and heart disease

Fig (4.c) – Comparison between sex and target feature

The correlation of the features is drawn in figure (4.d). The main purpose of the correlation plot is to define the positive and negative correlation between the features. In this figure we can see that how all the features taken correlates with target features.

Definition - A correlation matrix is a statistical technique used to evaluate the relationship between two variables in a dataset.

Fig (4.d) – Correlation Matrix of the attributes

Two strong correlations by cp and slope with target feature are studied statistically. As we can see in figure (4.e), there is no heart disease when the cp level is more than 350; however, heart disease is sustained more when

Fig (4.e) – cp v/s Target

the cp is between 200 and 250. In addition, when the slope is in $300 < \text{slope-1} < 350$, it shows that there is no disease, see figure (4.f). In contrast, for slope-2, there is a heart disease in $300 < \text{slope-2} < 350$.

Fig (4.f) – Slope v/s Target

B. Performance Analysis:

In this report, various machine learning algorithms like Logistic Regression (LR), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Random Forest classifier (RF) are studied broadly to predict the heart disease. The accuracy rate of each algorithm has been measured, and select the algorithm with the highest accuracy. After performing the machine learning algorithms for training and testing the dataset, we can find the better algorithm for by considering the accuracy rate. The rate of accuracy is calculated with the support of confusion matrix. As shown in the table 1, logistic regression algorithm gives the best accuracy to compare with other ML algorithms.

Table 1: Accuracy comparison of algorithms.

Algorithms	Accuracy
Logistic Regression	0.95
K-Nearest Neighbors	0.87
Random Forest	0.79

Table 2: f1-score, precision and recall of LR algorithm.

	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
0	0.94	0.97	0.96	34
1	0.96	0.93	0.94	27
Avg/Total	0.95	0.95	0.95	61

Fig (4.g) – Confusion Matrix of LR algorithm

V. Conclusions and Future scope

The heart is a vital organ in the human body; however, heart disease is a big problem in the world because this disease is increasing day by day. So, we can handle this disease if we have a model that can predict the initial heart disease status. So, we have to create a machine learning model that can be more accurate and help diagnose heart disease with less doubt and cost. It can be a primary technique for knowing the state of the heart. This work aims to predict the existence of heart diseases in patients according to specific health measurements. The report demonstrated 4 classification mechanisms create a prediction model. Data were collected and cleaned of any missing values and extreme outliers. In moreover, it was preprocessed to meet the model's requirements, where it went to different stages of visualization imbalances, obtaining the correlation matrix, using dimensionality reduction techniques and finally division using Hold-out. A model was trained and tested for each machine learning algorithm. This report focuses on the prediction of heart disease based on the accuracy rate of the confusion matrix. According to this idea, the statistics of the given algorithms follow is used to estimate the degree of accuracy of the permutation matrix a verified statistics between machine learning algorithms. When three algorithms are compared, it is found that the logistic regression algorithm is chosen with respect to performance with high accuracy. Accuracy rate of the logistic regression model is 95%, which suggests machine learning algorithm will be considered as a predefined tool for finding heart diseases in the near future. Other statistics such as f1-score, recall and precision rate calculated for logistic regression as 95%, 95% and 95%, respectively. These estimated values indicate the highest accuracy of this algorithm. These findings suggest that machine learning algorithms they can effectively learn about disease predictions. We can extend this kind of study to the diagnosis of other diseases. We can also analyse past data history and combine more machine learning techniques for better studying. Other possible applications of this study may include e.g., prediction of cardiovascular diseases, prediction of diabetes, breast cancer prediction, tumor prediction and multiple diseases predictions.

VI. References

- [1] Wikipedia contributors. (June 22, 2022). Machine learning. In Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia. Downloaded 06:31,26 June, 2022, from https://cs.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Machine_learning&oldid=1094363111.
- [2] Victor Chang, Vallabhanent Rupa Bhavani, Ariel Qianwen Xu, MA Hossain. An artificial intelligence model for heart disease detection using machine learning. *Healthcare analytics*, Volume 2, November 2022, 100016.
- [3] Ghumbre, S.U., & Ghatol, A.A. (2012). Heart disease diagnosis using a machine learning algorithm. In proceedings of international conference on the design of information systems and Intelligent Applications 2012 (INDIA 2012) were held in Visakhapatnam, India, January 2012 (pp. 217-225). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- [4] Rohit Bharti, Aditya Khamparia, Mohammed Shabaz, Gaurav Dhiman, Sagar pande and Parneet Singh. Prediction of the heart disease using a combination of machine learning and deep learning. *Computational Intelligence Hindi a Neuroscience*, Volume 2021, Article ID 8387680, 11 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/8387680>.
- [5] Khaled Mohamed Almustafa. Prediction of heart disease and sensitivity analysis of classifiers. *Almustafa BMC Bioinformatics* (2020) 21: 278. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12859-020-03626-y>.
- [6] Jee S H, Jang Y, Oh D J, Oh B H, Lee SH, Park S W & Yun Y D (2014), coronary heart disease prediction model. The Korean Heart Study. *BMJ open*, 4 (5), e005025.
- [7] Mai Shouman, Tim Turner and Rob Stocker. Use of Nearest Neighbor in the diagnosis of patients with heart disease. *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*, Vol. 2, No. 3, June 2012.
- [8] Ganna A, Magnusson PK, Pedersen NL, de Faire U, Reilly M, Arnlov J & Ingelsson E (2013). Multilocus genetic risk score for the prediction of ischemic heart disease. *Arteriosclerosis, Thrombosis and Vascular Biology*, 33(9), 2267-72.
- [9] Raihan M, Mondal S, More A, Sagor M O F, Sikder G, Majumder M A & Ghosh K (2016, December). Smartphone based on predicting the risk of ischemic heart disease (heart attack) using clinical data and data mining approaches, prototype design. 19th International Conference on Computers and Information Technology (ICCI) (pp. 299-303). IEEE.
- [10] Acharya U R, Fujita H, Oh SL, Hagiwara Y, Tan J H & Adam M (2017). Application of deep convolutional neural network for automatic detection of myocardial infarction using ECG signals. *Information Sciences*, 415, 190-8.
- [11] Takci H (2018). Improving prediction of heart attack feature selection methods. *Turkish Journal of Electrical Engineering & Computer Sciences*, 26 (1), 1-10.
- [12] Brown N, Young T, Gray D, Skene A M & Hampton J R (1997). Deaths of hospitalized patients due to acute myocardial infarction, 1982-92: analysis of heart attack data in Nottingham register, *BMJ*, 315 (7101), 159-64.
- [13] Soni J, Ansari U, Sharman D & Soni S (2011). Predictive data mining for medical diagnosis: an overview of heart disease forecast. *International Journal of Computer Applications*, 17 (8), 43-8.
- [14] Bashir S, Qamar U & Javed MY (2014, November). A file framework for intelligent decision support diagnosis of heart diseases. *International Conference on Information Society (i-Society 2014)* (pp. 259-64). IEEE.
- [15] Ordonez C (2006). Match discovering the rules with the train and a testing approach for predicting heart disease. *IEEE Transactions on Information Technologies in Biomedicine*, 10 (2), 334-43.
- [16] Wikipedia contributors. (June 21, 2022). Logistic regression. In Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia. Downloaded 06:36, June 26, 2022, from https://cs.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Logistic_regression&oldid=1094256072.
- [17] Wikipedia contributors. (2022, June 1). Linear regression. In Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia. Downloaded 06:39, 26 June, 2022, from https://cs.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Linear_regression&oldid=1091044459.
- [18] Wikipedia contributors. (2022, June 4). K-nearest neighbors algorithm. In Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia. Loaded 06:40, 26 June 2022, from https://cs.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Knext_neighbors_algorithm&oldid=1091525121.
- [19] Wikipedia contributors. (June 20, 2022). Random forest. In Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia. Downloaded 06:41, 26 June, 2022, from https://cs.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Random_forest&oldid=1094130824.
- [20] Wikipedia contributors. (2022, June 15). Decision tree learning. In Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia. Loaded 06:42, 26 June 2022, from https://cs.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Decision_tree_learning&oldid=10933164.
- [21] A C, R. ., V. . V, K. . K, S. . H, and P. S. . E. "In-Cabin Radar Monitoring System: Detection and Localization of People Inside Vehicle Using Vital Sign Sensing Algorithm". *International Journal on Recent and Innovation Trends in Computing and Communication*, vol. 10, no. 8, Aug. 2022, pp. 104-9, doi:10.17762/ijritcc.v10i8.5682.

- [22] V. V, R. A. C, S. B. M, A. Kumari P, V. S. Reddy R and S. Murthy R, "Custom Hardware and Software Integration: Bluetooth Based Wireless Thermal Printer for Restaurant and Hospital Management," 2022 IEEE 2nd Mysore Sub Section International Conference (MysuruCon), Mysuru, India, 2022, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/MysuruCon55714.2022.9972714.
- [23] V. V, R. A. C, V. S. R. R, A. K. P, S. M. R and S. B. M, "Implementation of IoT in Agriculture: A Scientific Approach for Smart Irrigation," 2022 IEEE 2nd Mysore Sub Section International Conference (MysuruCon), Mysuru, India, 2022, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/MysuruCon55714.2022.9972734.
- [24] Viswanatha, V., and R. Venkata Siva Reddy. "Digital control of buck converter using arduino microcontroller for low power applications." 2017 International Conference On Smart Technologies For Smart Nation (SmartTechCon). IEEE, 2017.
- [25] Viswanatha, V., Venkata Siva Reddy, R., Rajeswari (2020). Research on State Space Modeling, Stability Analysis and PID/PIDN Control of DC–DC Converter for Digital Implementation. In: Sengodan, T., Murugappan, M., Misra, S. (eds) Advances in Electrical and Computer Technologies. Lecture Notes in Electrical Engineering, vol 672. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-5558-9_106.